

Adaptive physical don't forget pedagogical functions

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Abstract: this is it in the article adaptive physical education pedagogical functions about the word was conducted.

Key Words: adaptive physical education, pedagogy influence, support movement, function.

Our republic to independence from achieving then disabled people to sports big attention is being given. Disabled our athletes Asia and the world in competitions good to the results reached Uzbekistan the flag high are raising. Physical opportunity limited children between strong ingenuity owners, spiritually rich, scientific potential to increase in life own place to find movement doing young people many is found. Without arms and legs, eyes or of the organism which one member of not working, strong work or poem typewrite , computer , television setup or to the norm delivered tune which creates our youth many we will meet . Four mucha be healthy standing up to his family, neighborhood, society from profit according to more loss which brings spiritual poor we also meet young people can

Adaptive physical education (AJT) - functional, that's it including action opportunities absolute or long for a period of time lost people physical education different aspects learning science.

of the disabled training process healthy athletes training from the process difference effect to be object movement possibilities them apply field limited without of the organism different in systems steady defects there is people is considered That's why for sports training for the disabled his own specialized features have Theirs essence adaptive and compensator mechanisms of formation base calculated physical posture , sports technique improvement in the process movement actions , physical adjectives and download systematic correction out of necessity consists of

Adaptive of sports main active private training functions (developmental , correctional - compensatory , education , training , rehabilitation) coming private training of the process features looking we go out Adaptive sports training for initial conditions the following is considered : to the athlete and in the chosen sport

pedagogical effects to the system directly concerned has been medical indicators and against indicators , solid motivation , interest and functional orientation , injury or another from injury next recovery - treatment events as a result achieved physical of the situation stability .

General work of ability level reflection which coordination abilities, muscle, strength, flexibility, flexibility, endurance, vital important movement qualifications and physical adjectives fund restore landmarks is considered In the chosen sport specialized direction physical download in execution physical work ability movement field quality integral indicators of the state is counted . Sports equipment mastery disabled - athletes of preparation the most important and the most complicated organize doer is considered His essence own movement abilities biomechanical, physiological, anatomical, psychological and another laws based on effective from use consists of Action each how appearance an athlete in space shift with depends Shift without devices (swimming), devices with (sports games), performance on devices (carts) . can Sportsman device with active mutually in effect to be of shifting basis is considered The basis is movement apparatus damaged and blind - disabled people technique in mastering much difficulties to the body will come . The basis is movement apparatus damaged in disabled people technique improvement in the process of actions biomechanics and anatomical structures (hand amputation when done special mechanisms and technical from devices using in prostheses , in sports carts shift) re . In the blind while vision sensor system damaged because of technical preparation difficulties in space landmark to get , to move speed and accuracy , balance , tension of stratification and another coordination manifestation of being violation with depends Technique of learning methodical methods individual correction of actions to do and broken functions new movement programs make up at the expense of compensation to do the way with done is increased .

of the technique each one elements known function perform, external view shape and each to a sport special has been has characteristics (spatial, time, dynamic, rhythmic). A disabled athlete high results showing of technique variant individual technique style formation for the most comfortable type is a sports technique appropriation yet high to the results to achieve because it does not guarantee him done increase of the organism functional preparation level with is determined. of the organism functional preparation level vegetative systems (breath take, blood rotation)

and physical development of quality (strength, flexibility, speed, dexterity, endurance) with is provided. of the disabled physical of preparation features of the organism all functions wide complex effect transfer with one in line pathological breakdown as a result damaged muscle groups, functional system and coordination abilities local correction regularly done is increased.

Exercise in the process movement violations correction and compensation physical without loading using done is increased. In this download common and local influence, being used of exercises coordination complexity, power, orientation, size, intensity, re in effect recovery intervals will be changed. Adequacy and optimality, basic principles is considered and them done increase sure and modern pedagogical of the matter disabled athlete situation rational planning and fast control to do with is determined .

To the goal directed pedagogical effect in the process physiological functions stimulus (simulation) is given and doctor-pedagogue control within done increase need This is training programs to the individual capabilities of athletes directed to be need and leader of functions status dynamics about objective to information have to be need Stratified approach based on training process individualization of the disabled training process important feature is considered Stratified approach disabled - athletes their pathology , age , gender , training level , voluntary manifestation to do features and another qualities in consideration received without to groups to combine means Stratified approach to the coach excess download prevention get , athletes interests and motivations in consideration get , communicate style , practice adequate methods , download of management effective methods choose opportunity will give . Individualization movement possibilities one series medical , psychological , physiological and pedagogical factors with limited only one to the individual special was features in consideration to receive means Medical factors row is this main diagnosis , medical perspective , on the way diseases , tension muscle to work against pointers , saved of functions condition , psychological factors between - motivation, emotional - volitional condition , mental of functions (attention , reception of doing , of memory and others) level , psychological suitable drop off i.e small in a group , in a team enters Physiological to factors body structure anthropometric indicators , movement activity which provides vegetative system (heart - blood rotation , breath get) functional condition , general work of ability status and muscle activities energetic supply , movement and coordination do not spoil (intellectual the field

violation of the sensor system defects , disorders combinations - combinations) character and their status enters Pedagogical to factors the following characteristics includes : movement of the function and actions of coordination saved level, physical development and physical preparation indicators , learning level and to study actions (sports technique , tactics). readiness , training level and others

It is mentioned above factors collection plan disabled people to sports in preparation in consideration get pedagogue - coach pedagogical of the program strategy and tactics formation , training effects fast management , athlete situation and sports results perspective opportunity will give of the disabled active sports practice wide knowledge system Demand does and they are of preparation all sides, to the organism physical of exercises effect laws , control and own himself control methods, private possibilities and abilities about objective data based on structure because it is necessary athlete - disabled object and of activity subject is considered However , it is adaptive of sports education function only athlete - disabled own his body , movements , himself attitude , emotions to manage smooth from taking over not but the main one this process his for whole life during necessary demand organize which to the worldview also consists of turning .

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